

Multiple stressors

Global warming, marine heatwaves, ocean acidification and pollutants are major stressors in the Arctic marine ecosystems. These stressors can interact to intensify each other's effects. However, we know very little about how these stressors may affect key Arctic zooplankton species such as *Calanus* copepods. These little zooplanktonic animals are an important food source for Arctic fish, seabirds and marine mammals, therefore the effects of multiple stressors on *Calanus* copepods will likely be cascading through the Arctic marine food web.

The effects of multiple stressors on *Calanus* copepods

4°C warming or a reduced 0.5 pH unit from ocean acidification did not seem to affect survival and reproduction of *Calanus* copepods.

Exposure to pyrene, a common oil substance, decreased the survival and reproduction of *Calanus* copepods. The pyrene effect could last a year after exposure.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For *Calanus glacialis*, warming and ocean acidification increased the negative effect of pyrene on copepod survival.

For the much larger *Calanus hyperboreus*, the cumulative effect of stressors on survival was much less pronounced.

Studies that are performed across a series of stress levels and exposure conditions that take into account seasonal changes in the temperature and ocean acidification will particularly be important to tease apart the effects of these stressors on accumulation and toxicity of pollutants on Arctic marine species. A step further is to determine the early changes of stressor effects on different levels of biological organization, from molecular markers to communities, that are essential as early warming signs. Ultimately, identifying the ecological tipping points of Arctic marine species and food webs under the complex interactions of global warming, marine heatwaves, ocean acidification and pollutants is crucial for more comprehensive ecological risk assessments and management.